

MAINTENANCE AND OTHER OPERATING EXPENSES (MOOE) AND SCHOOL BASED MANAGEMENT (SBM) PERFORMANCE OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN SAMAR ISLAND

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ABSTRACT—The study investigated the extent of Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) utilization relating to School Based Management (SBM) performance of public secondary schools in Samar Island for school years 2016-2019. A mixed method, explanatory research design was employed utilizing 159 school heads. Focus Group Discussion (FGD) was conducted for selected School heads, disbursing officers or bookkeepers and teacher representatives from six divisions in Samar Island. Quantitatively, this study made use of percentages, weighted mean, and Pearson r for the correlative data; while thematic analysis enriched the qualitative investigation. Findings of this study highlights a high extent of MOOE utilization to ensure students' access to complete basic education; priority for school ceremonies like the Moving Up of the Junior High School, Closing Ceremonies, and Recognition Programs; to support the needs of the learners for their learning activities; to fund the rentals and minor repairs of tools and equipment that are important to classroom activities; and to fund the expenses related to graduation rites. The results showed that the least priority in the expenses were for the Internet connection of the school, telephone bills, salaries for the janitors, and the security guards. In addition, it was also found out that the SBM performance of the schools have improved in the past three years, from Good to Better. Finally, no substantial connection prevailed between the extent of utilization of MOOE and SBM performance of secondary schools in Samar Island.

Keywords—MOOE, SBM, Mixed method design, Best Practices, Intervention Scheme, Public Secondary Schools, Samar Island

I. INTRODUCTION

Effective school heads are robust and strong teachers, their nature of work is to secure the primary matters focusing to the learning and teaching actions, activities and schedules as well as the unceasing development for school. Assimilating teamwork, vivid and measurable goal, the methodical and organized collection and analysis of performance data that constitution to the underpinning positive and development outcomes consequently.

The Department of Education (DepEd) with over half a million people employed, is labeled to be one of the most dishonest agencies in the Philippines suffering from serious implementation discrepancies (Abad, 2005; Carin˜o, Iglesias, & Mendoza, 1998). Tomacruz (2019) stressed that lack of

classrooms, overworked teachers, shortages of school buildings and instructional materials and the likes are some challenges confronting the education sector nowadays. These realities were accorded in the accounts of the Income Generating Projects (IGP). Education Act of 1982 describes the right of school administrators (all persons in policy implementing positions including principals) to submit proposals to have income generating projects and eventually claim the outcome of the projects as all schools are entitled to acquire support (Chapter 5, Sec. 39). In the study of Ochada et.al. (2018) generating an atmosphere of trust in the school ensues adequate performance of teachers and students. Moreover, the School Head who is transparent and

openboosts the participation and commitment of the teachers to help improve the school in general.

Statement of the Problem

This study analyzed the association concerning the utilization of Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) and School Based Management (SBM) Performance of secondary schools in Samar Island for SYs 2016-2019.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of utilization for Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) of secondary schools when classified to:
 - 1.1 Funding activities in the School Improvement Plan (SIP) and Annual Improvement Plan (AIP) of the schools;
 - 1.2 Financing expenses pertaining to graduation rites, moving up or closing ceremonies and recognition of the school;
 - 1.3 Funding supplies, rental and minor repair of tools and equipment necessary in the conduct of classes and learning activities
 - 1.4 Funding utilities of the school and other correspondence; and
 - 1.5 Compensating for janitorial and security services of the schools?
2. What is the level of School Based Management (SBM) performance of secondary schools in the study?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of utilization of MOOE and the SBM performance of secondary schools?
4. What are the best practices in the utilization of MOOE in the area of study?
5. What intervention scheme may be proposed based on the findings of the study?

Scope and delimitation

This study determined the extent on the utilization on MOOE and the SBM practices of secondary schools in the Samar Island which comprised of six (6) divisions. Three (3) city divisions namely, Borongan, Catbalogan and Calbayog

and another three (3) schools division offices namely, Eastern Samar, Western Samar and Northern Samar. This study was done in the school year 2019-2020.

The extent of MOOE utilization has been based from the survey assessment to school heads and to be validated thru an FGD or Focus Group Discussion as to best practices in which key informants were school heads, disbursing Officers and or bookkeepers and teacher representatives. Meanwhile, the data on school based management performances were taken as secondary data which focus on SBM practice obtained in their respective division offices. The researcher had a strong inclination in obtaining a copy of SBM performance in three (3) consecutive years. Whatever data were obtained are the only ones available.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Quality education is essential in the child's preservation of the Philippine culture; and economic well-being and substantial resources contribute to quality education.

Republic Act 9155 recognizes school heads the capacity to execute instructional and administrative supervision of the school. This law points out that school leader has these functions: (1) Personnel, physical and fiscal resources administration; (2) Acceptance of donations in updating teaching competencies, school facilities and providing instructional materials and equipment. This function includes financial management function. Fiscal resources refer to school finances which include the appropriated budgetary allocation for the school (Official Gazette, 2001).

DepEd Order No. 12 (2016) defines the MOOE as the school budget from the government which is given to all public schools. Procurement of school supplies, payment for utilities and expense in communication, training activities, recognition and graduation rites, security, janitorial services, and minor school repair compose this allocation. These items are stated in the approved School Improvement Plan (SIP) and the Annual Improvement Plan (AIP) of the school. In addition, the Order demands apt and ideal use of school

resources and mechanisms to project transparency and accountability. Considerably, all schools are governed by Republic Act 9485 (Anti-Red Tape Act of 2007) to post a Transparency Board on MOOE.

Moreover, DepEd Order No. 13 dictates all school heads to assume the ensuing duties: (1) state all sources of funding of the school allocated in the MOOE; (2) outline the projected use of all sources of funds; (3) disseminate publicly the sources in the transparency board and update the information every three months (4) relay officially the sources and uses of school funds to the stakeholders. The ability to manage MOOE is best perceived in the mechanisms of the schools daily. With the appropriation of funds, school leaders are empowered to operate and maintain the school. This then makes the principals more accountable because of the blanket authority given to them. On the other hand, if the organization is lax with accountability, uncertainties, irregularities and unjust behaviors will be commonplace. Therefore, accountability identifies what resources were used by the school staff taking into considerations the parameters to reach the organizational goals. On the flipside, accountability should also reveal the shortfalls and errors in the given services and hopefully identifies the culprits correctly.

The mission, vision, and goals stated in DepEd, despite the challenging task led an organization, school heads in public institution were finding means to achieve the abovementioned. Apart from these trails comprise is the liquidation of MOOE. Considerably, in the article of Mayor (2019), in the DepEd Schools Division of Cebu, the school head in certain public school disclosed that the delay of liquidation of the MOOE are due to absence of canvassers, means of transportation, carpenters or workers to do repairs, insufficient MOOE funds for repair, delay of releasing of checks, and, time. All these concerns worsen the task of the administrator in the demand of a transparent MOOE usage. Certainly, these are just some of the many other struggles that a school head encounters in taking risks to achieve goals of the Education department.

The school heads need to solve many managerial problems adding to the delay in liquidating cash advances. Other problems will never occur if the common problems are solved.

In public schools in the Philippines, matters and concerns regarding the utilization of MOOE continue to prevail as there are some teachers claim the presence of shady transactions on this issue. The condition gets worsen when Income Generating Projects (IGP's) was taken into consideration. Whereas, IGPs should be considered to augment and solve the scarcity of funds. School administrators, or all persons occupying policy implanting position, which include the school heads are given the authority by virtue of Education Act (1982) to draft or create proposals and claim the outcome from income generating projects.

III. METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the methodology used by the researcher in completing the study. This includes research design, sampling technique, respondents, sources of data and data analysis of the study. Construction of the instrument, validation, administration and retrieval of the instrument were also included.

Research Design

The mixed method design was employed in the conduct of the study. Specifically, it employed the explanatory sequential mixed method design. This type of method provides research questions to uncover with unspecified facets of a phenomenon and are answered with information given in statistical and descriptive forms. In addition, requiring at least two research questions is a unique aspect of any given mixed method study (Subedi, 2016).

Furthermore, Schoonenboom & Johnson (2017) states that mixed methods display combined features of both qualitative and quantitative research approaches for the extensive purposes of breadth and profundity of acceptance and justification.

Quantitative data was gathered first followed by a qualitative data. After which, the two types of data were converged into

just one finding. This would form a mixed finding composed of a quantitative data and a qualitative data.

Population and Sample

The respondents of the study were selected through stratified random sampling process. The selection of the number of respondents was accomplished through the Slovin's sampling formula.

In getting the extent of MOOE utilization, school heads were the respondents from different public secondary schools in Samar Island. Based on the record from Eastern Visayas Regional Office, the total number of secondary schools within Samar Island were 263. City of Borongan has seven (7), Calbayog City has twenty seven (27), Catbalogan City also has seven (7), For Eastern Samar it has fifty four (54), Northern Samar, eighty six (86) and Samar consists of eighty two (82). For this study, with the aid of Slovin's sampling formula, the respondents were reduced to 159. Meanwhile, for Focus Group Discussion (FGD) purposes, all the school heads, disbursing officers or bookkeepers and a teacher representative from the thirteen (13) different public secondary schools in Samar Island were included in the research investigation as sample key informants and they were selected thru categorization of small, medium and large schools.

Instrumentation

The main research instrument was a researcher made questionnaire crafted based on DepEd Order guidelines on MOOE utilization indicators. The preliminary parts of the questionnaire include the communication letter and question items on the respondent's name, school, and position or designation. Furthermore, the first part of the questionnaire asked about the extent of utilization of the MOOE. The respondents are requested to rate each item on a score from 1 to 5, 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest. The questionnaire on MOOE utilization involved five components namely: funding activities in the SIP and AIP of the schools, financing expenses pertaining to graduation rites, funding supplies, rental and minor repair of tools and equipment, funding utilities of the school and other

correspondence, and compensating for janitorial and security services of the schools.

In seeking data for SBM performance, the researcher treated these as secondary data, where he sought a request from SBM Coordinators of the different Division Offices in Samar Island. The components include leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement and management of resources.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Jay Barney's Resource Based View (RBV) Theory accentuating on an inside-out method for organizational analysis with consideration to organization being a bundle of resources. It underlines that organizational difference happens due to the way combination of these resources is done. This theory basically specifies that evaluating an organization should start from its core environment. Strategic choice, charging the management with the vital tasks of classifying, designing, and deploying key resources to maximize returns is emphasized in this theory. In relation to Department of Education, this is a managerial model utilized to describe the strategic resources the school can use to get maintainable and aggressive advantage. DepEd endures crafting more resources to be used to support the schools in instilling a better avenue for students' learnability. Number of teachers, students and classrooms managed by the school and even the fixed amount to provide for the basic needs of a school are several predictors affecting school operations. As such, schools are directed to manage the school operations in a better, more adaptable, more agreeable self-government approach.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS & RESULTS

6. Summary of Findings

The treatment of data reveals the following essential findings.

1. Extent of MOOE utilization based on implementing guidelines.

Among the items on the extent of MOOE utilization, the respondents highly utilized the fund for the access to complete basic education with the mean ($\bar{x}$ = 4.81). This is a

very enlightening result because it shows that the respondents are focused and committed to providing the best possible and complete basic education they could give to their students. While the lowest mean went to the utilization of the MOOE on the Internet needs of the school ($\bar{x}=3.38$). The rural nature of the communities in the island has hampered the development of the Internet infrastructure most likely because the demand for Internet service is not as big as the bigger urban areas in the Philippines. The educational impact of the Internet is not straightforward. The issue of unequal access to the most enabling and empowering forms of Internet use remains a major concern.

2. School Based Management performance of secondary schools in the area of study.

For SY 2016-2017, the SBM performance weighted mean was 1.42 which is Good. It improved by 26% in the next school year to 1.79 which is Better. In 2018-2019, it slipped by around 7% to 1.68 which is still Better. The data shows that the SBM performance of the schools have at least improved in the past three years, from Good to Better.

Secondary schools of Samar Island have provided a better system of leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement and management or resources in achieving shared vision, mission, and goals for schools to be responsive and proactive to diverse environment.

3. Relationship between the extent of utilization of MOOE and the SBM performance of secondary schools.

Results revealed a correlation coefficient value of 0.077 with a corresponding p-value of 0.336 interpreted as Not Significant. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the MOOE Utilization and SBM Performance of Secondary Schools in Samar Island was not rejected since the p value is greater than our level of significance which is .005. This result implies that the MOOE Utilization of Secondary Schools' MOOE Utilization is not related to their SBM Performance.

4. Best practices in the utilization of MOOE in the area of study.

From the narrations of the participants in thirteen (13) focus group discussions (FGD), major themes emerged as follows; (1) MOOE Practices, (2) Efficient Management Functions, (3) Quality Teaching and Learning Process, (4) Legal Foundation, and (5) Relevant School Operations.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn.

1. The MOOE has been an important asset that the school heads have used in order to give good learning experiences to their students.
2. The school heads have top priority for the following areas with regard to MOOE utilization – provide complete basic education, funding expenses of the school related to moving up, recognition and graduation ceremonies of the different grade levels in the school.
3. Since the MOOE is finite in value, the school heads have spent the least on the Internet connection of the school and compensating utility personnel and security guards.
4. School heads limit their expenditures related to the MOOE to the approved list in the SIP. This way of practice stifles the innovative aspect of teacher leadership and undermines the autonomy which should have been given to each of the schools in terms of how they are going to spend their MOOEs.
5. As to significant relationship between the MOOE Utilization and SBM Performance of Secondary Schools in Samar Island, study revealed not significantly related.

RECOMANDATION

In the light of the foregoing conclusions, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

1. School heads must coordinate the with the plans and programs of national and local government units in the provision of remarkable educational opportunities to learners and have to get the best Internet connection provided by the telecommunication companies serving the region using the funding from the MOOE. This is in line with their commitment to give the best learning experiences to their

students who, now, have to use the blended learning approach due to the limitations placed on face-to-face learning.

2. Increase awareness among the school heads to beef up their science laboratories even if they are not offering the STEM strand. The lack of standard laboratory equipment in the public schools hinders the process of innovation and creativity of the students.

3. Continue to prioritize and give importance to the quality of the 'Graduation Rites, Moving Up or Closing Ceremonies and Recognition of the School'. These are very important occasions for the students and their parents as they serve as a showcase of the school, hence they must continue to give proper funding to these ceremonies as their conduct will reflect greatly on the school's leadership.

4. Keep proper records of the forecasting made by previous school heads and put them in the SIP to ensure that there is accuracy and completeness in the data especially for fixed expenses like the utilities.

5. Recommend to the Division Office (DO) that the SBM performance record every school year is updated by the SBM Coordinator and that the data is properly endorsed to the next appointed person. This is to ensure there is completeness, accuracy, and continuity in the data which researchers might need in future studies.

6. That future researchers look into improving the spending on the teachers' professional development using the MOOE to help improve the performance of the school.

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